

CULTURAL SCIENCES

GENDER ISSUES IN THE LATEST GEORGIAN THEATRE (AUGUST STRINDBERG'S *MISS JULIE* INTERPRETED BY LEVAN TSULADZE)

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Abstract

One of the founders of the new drama, August Strindberg's dramaturgy cannot be attributed to any specific direction. An experimenter by nature, he was constantly looking for new themes, structures, and forms of drama. In his theoretical works, he argued the need to create a new drama and performing arts, which should combine the best traditions of the classics with innovation.

Strindberg sensed the beginning of the crisis in society - along with the technical progress and the development of life, a person confronts not the society (as in Ibsen's plays), but another person, the closest to him, in whom he sees a competitor and tries to establish himself by fighting with him.

Gender issues exist in more than one of Strindberg's works, including *Miss Julie* (*Fröken Julie*).

For several years, Levan Tsuladze has been exploring the problem of violence in society with his performances, in which violence against women and the issues of women's rights occupy an important place. For this problem Tsuladze's staging: *The Kreutzer Sonata* (according to Lev Tolstoy), *Crime and Punishment* (according to Fyodor Dostoevsky), *The Marriage of Figaro* (Pierre-Augustin Caron de Beaumarchais) - in the Marjanishvili Theatre, *Othello* (Shakespeare), and *Miss Julie* - in the Theatre Factory 42.

Strindberg characterizes Miss Julie as a half-woman, a weak creature, a spreader of evil, who is not destined to have a long life. In the end, the playwright created the face of a strong person. And Christine, the cook, is described as a woman with slave psychology.

Miss Julie, staged according to the interpretation of Levan Tsuladze, is a drama brought to the point of tragedy. The director, transforming the text of the play into a stage text, changed the images of Julie and Christine by shifting the accents. They are neither weak nor „nature's mistakes“ nor „monsters“. They, with their different origins, erudition, and methods, fight for their rights and their future. It is true, that Julie kills herself, but this suicide is not equal to defeat but to victory. Because Julie is the forerunner of those women who, shortly after her suicide, received the right to participate in elections.

Keywords: Strindberg, a new drama, theatrical forms, gender theme, Levan Tsuladze, interpretation, performance.

Introduction

August Strindberg's boisterous, constantly searching for new, tireless, contradictory spirit is vividly reflected in his work. He was a multi-talented person: prose writer, playwright, theatre theorist, poet, historian, archaeologist, ethnographer, biologist, chemist. Of course, prose and dramaturgy, theatre theory are the pinnacle of his creativity. He spent his entire conscious life in search of the truth, his aspirations and search can be compared to Goethe's Faust. He was a strange person, a maximalist by nature, he didn't obey anything, including state structures, which is why he had to stay in exile for years. He experienced everything painfully, the family traumas he suffered in childhood affected not only his personal qualities but also his creativity.

Along with Ibsen, Hauptmann, Zola, Maeterlinck, Shaw, and Chekhov, Strindberg is the founder of the new drama. The authors of the new drama changed the problematics, form, and structure of the drama, the traditional, old theatre system that had been formed over the centuries. New perception, analysis, and depiction in a different way of feelings, aspirations, and thoughts of a modern man, and his relationship with the outside world contributed to the emergence and development

of several new trends (naturalism, symbolism, impressionism, expressionism, intellectual drama, etc.) in the XIX-XX centuries.

Strindberg's dramaturgy cannot be attributed to any particular direction. He has created: historical dramas, as well as plays of a naturalistic, psychological, and social nature. He used symbolic techniques and mystical elements in his works. He was an experimenter, constantly looking for new themes, new structures, and forms of drama.

„As a poet, thinker, prophet, and mediator of a new worldview, he was too much of a forerunner for his work to seem in the slightest way out of date. Unaffiliated with the schools and currents of that time, he united in himself their main features. A naturalist and neo-romantic, he precedes expressionism; all the representatives of that generation are indebted to him. At the same time, he is also the first surrealist - the first in all senses. But there is a lot of tradition in his innate avant-garde. As a naturalist and mystic, he continues - though, of course, in a very personal manner - the line of the Swedish 18th century. He is a worthy successor to Celsius, Linnaeus, and Swedenborg, which is evident in his impressive work - in *Swedish Events and Adventures*,

in the *Historical Miniatures*, in ten Swedish Royal Dramas. As an interpreter and shaper of the history of his country, he is deeply immersed in the past.¹ This is how Thomas Mann evaluated the writer's work a dozen years later.

Due to disagreements with the authorities, Strindberg was forced to leave Sweden and from 1883 he traveled to various European countries, which further enriched the views of the writer and finally convinced him of the need to transform drama and theatrical art. For him the existing dramaturgy and theatrical forms were degraded, even dead.

„It seems to me that the theatre, like religion, is about to be discarded as a dying form of art, which we lack the necessary preconditions to enjoy. This supposition is supported by the pervasive theatre crisis now prevailing throughout Europe, and not least because in England and Germany, those cultural heartlands which have nurtured the greatest thinkers of our age, drama is dead, along with most of the other fine arts“.²

Methods

The method of historical-typological and comparative analysis used in the article allowed me to research Strindberg's views on new drama and performing arts, modern theatre, and the playwright's attitude toward gender issues. How his theoretical views were reflected in the dramatic work, namely in *Miss Julie*. What forms and techniques did Levan Tsuladze use when interpreting Strindberg's play. How the director transformed the text of the play into a stage text in the performance staged in the Theatre Factory 42 and changed the gender balance, the characters of Julie and Christine through the tasks given to the actors only by shifting the accents.

Reasoning

Strindberg's theoretical thinking on dramaturgy, theatre art, its goals, and tasks is mainly formulated in the introduction to *Miss Julie* (1888), which is considered a manifesto of the new dramaturgy, as well as in the articles: „On Modern Drama and Modern Theatre“, 1889, „Memorandum to the Members of the Intimate Theatre from the Director“, 1908 and „Open Letters to the Intimate Theatre“, 1908).³ In his theoretical works and letters, Strindberg substantiated the need to create a new drama and stage art, which should organically combine the best traditions of the classics and the innovation of a modern creator. In 1907, Strindberg brought to life theoretical ideas about the forms of performing arts, creating „Intimate Theatre“, which existed for several years. While creating the new, Strindberg destroyed everything old and outdated.

„Destruction was Strindberg's element. He was a genius-hammer, a genius-dynamite. To find a harbor, shelter, and peace, this hammer, this dynamite, broke and tore everything. Always full of hatred, beyond hysterical anger, he hid an immense, boundless love, love that cannot be extinguished.“⁴

Because of his jealous nature, Strindberg did not have a happy personal life. He was married several times. His first wife Siri von Essen (whom, it should be noted, he „stealed“ from another man) was an actress. The second wife Frida Uhl (23 years younger) was a writer, playwright, and translator, and the third wife Harriet Bosse (30 years younger) was a Norwegian actress. His last love, Fanny Falkner, was only 17 years old. Every time the marriage and the relationship with women failed. He was jealous not only of his spouses but even of his children, some of whom he declared were not his.

When researching Strindberg's prose and dramatic works, letters, and articles, one concludes that he was a misogynist, but it is impossible to discuss this issue unilaterally. One of Strindberg's researchers writes: „Strindberg's relationship with women in his life seems to have been generally complicated, as his divorces testify. Strindberg has often been identified as a misogynist, but the justification for this has, in recent years, increasingly been questioned. Eivor Martinus has – in the book *Little Devil, Little Angel* reviewed a large body of letters between Strindberg and his women. Martinus concludes that Strindberg could not possibly have hated women, although he was often in conflict with them.“⁵

In general, the end and beginning of a century is considered to be a period of strong transitions, among other things, it concerns both social and cultural life. The end of the XIX century and the beginning of the XX century was an era of fundamental, unprecedented, radical changes. Everything old was destroyed and something that did not exist before was created. Technical progress gave birth to something completely new. Creators participated in this process. They liked many things in these changes, however, along with progressive changes, they were afraid of loss of spirituality in a man, and neglect of individuality. In the introduction to *Miss Julie*, Strindberg wrote: „But the time may come when we shall have become so highly developed, so enlightened, that we shall be able to look with indifference at the brutal, cynical, heartless drama that life presents when we shall have laid aside those inferior, unreliable instruments of thought called feelings, which will become superfluous and harmful once our organs of judgment have matured.“⁶

¹ Mann, T. (1961) Август Стриндберг. Статьи 1929-1955гг. Т. 10. Москва. (Mann, T. (1961) August Strindberg. Articles 1929-1955 Vol. 10. Moscow.)

² Strindberg A. (2007) Preface to *Miss Julie*, Strindberg on Drama and Theatre (selected, translated, and edited by Egil Törnqvist and Birgitta Steene), „Amsterdam University Press“. p. 62.

³ Strindberg A. (2007) Strindberg on Drama and Theatre (selected, translated, and edited by Egil Törnqvist and Birgitta Steene), „Amsterdam University Press“. p. 79-84; 125-135; 158-165.

⁴ Луначарский, А. (1965), Великомученик индивидуализма (Август Стриндберг), Собр. соч. Т. 5. Москва. (Lunacharsky, A. (1965), The Great Martyr of Individualism (August Strindberg), Collected Works. Vol. 5. Moscow.)

⁵ Arntzen, E. (2014) Misogyny and Vampirism in Strindberg, Gender and Scandinavian Studies: Language, Literature, Social Relations. An International Conference. April 30 – May 2. Javakhishvili Tbilisi State University. https://old.tsu.ge/data/file_db/scandinavian-studies/Even-Arntzen.pdf (30.09.2024).

⁶ Strindberg A. (2007) Preface to *Miss Julie*, Strindberg on Drama and Theatre (selected, translated, and edited by Egil

He notices this dangerous tendency not only in society but also in the relations between men and women. Strindberg devoted most of his work to the study of the gender problem and presented the relationship between the genders in a completely different way.

„In the second half of the 19th century, the theme of gender was reflected in world dramaturgy to a certain extent. This is the period when Sigmund Freud appeared in Western consciousness with his Psychoanalysis, which to some extent impacted dramaturgy. A good example of this is the play *Miss Julie* by Swedish playwright August Strindberg, one inspired by Freud's theories of sex and the eternal struggle between the sexes... Despite sharing Freud's phallogocentric ideas, Strindberg's dramaturgy makes a significant contribution to the development of gender drama. In contrast, Norwegian playwright Henrik Ibsen directly supports the recognition of women's rights and because of this is under great pressure and persecution from society.“⁷

The playwright removed the romantic mask from the relationship between men and women that existed for centuries, exposed it, and presented the struggle between the genders as an acute conflict. In his work, these two, once harmoniously united into one whole, appeared to us as sworn enemies of each other. They are engaged in a life-and-death struggle for self-establishment.

Strindberg sensed the beginnings of a crisis in European society and even seemed to predict its future. Technical progress was accompanied by the problem of human loneliness and alienation, unsociability, against which a society devoid of feelings was powerless. The playwright, in the complex collisions of life, studied the psychology of people, the essence and goals of their actions. With the development of life, the individual confronts not society (as it is in Ibsen's plays), but the other person, closest to him, in whom he sees a competitor and tries to assert himself by fighting with him.

In the introduction to *Miss Julie* Strindberg wrote: „As modern characters, living in an age of transition more hectic and hysterical than the one that preceded it, I have depicted my figures as more split and vacillating, a mixture of the old and the new, and it seems to me not improbable that modern ideas may even have permeated down to the level of servants via newspapers and conversations.“⁸

We find gender issues in more than one of Strindberg's works (prose, dramaturgy, journalism), including *Miss Julie*. The psychological and plot collisions, tension, and intensity of the energetic charge of *Miss*

Julie have determined its popularity in different countries (*Miss Julie* is the most frequently staged of Strindberg's plays).

„Initially, this play was met with great opposition in Europe because of the topics that the author talks about sexuality, the constant struggle between the sexes, and women who want to finally be equal to men. Strindberg's work was introduced to Georgian readers at the end of the 19th century, though his dramaturgy was staged in the Georgian theater quite late, and Georgian theater-makers do not favor this author much even today.“⁹

Several interesting interpretations of this play have been created in Georgia in the modern Georgian theatre - in 2012 Data Tavadze staged it in the Royal District Theatre, in 2017 Ilia Korkashvili in the Gori Giorgi Eristavi State Drama Theatre, in 2021, Sofo Kelbakiani in the Theatre on Atoneli.

Miss Julie staged in 2024 at the Theatre Factory 42 with the interpretation of Levan Tsuladze is a drama brought to the point of tragedy, with an emphasis on human values, relationships between people, women and men, women and women, parents and children, results of childhood trauma. The director transferred the text of the play to the stage almost unchanged, except for a few cuts. The performance is focused on the ensemble of actors: direction, scenography, choreography, digital visual effects or video installations, musical arrangement serves to present the characters created by the actors.

The action (as in the play) takes place in the kitchen. There is nothing excessive in Levan Tsuladze's scenography - a kitchen table, shelves for storing wine bottles, an oven, a refrigerator, and a few chairs. The screen stretched across the back wall, with a video installation by Data Dvalishvili and digital visuals by Levan Geliashvili, shows sometimes a forest landscape with rustling leaves on the trees, a black hole with white tentacles (perhaps a solar eclipse). Sometimes the image disappears, and the stripes appear on the TV screen when the signal is damaged, with hissing sounds.

The servant Jean (Paata Papuashvili) turns to the cook Christine (Anuki Grigolia) – „Miss Julie is mad again tonight – absolutely mad!“ This is where the love relationship between Christine and Jean becomes clear. At this time, Ana Vasadze's *Miss Julie* appears on the stage in a glittering golden dress, dancing with headphones (choreographer Tinatin Tsuladze). A triangle is formed, and from the very first scene, the „struggle“ for

Törnqvist and Birgitta Steene), „Amsterdam University Press“. p. 63.

⁷ კვინიკაძე, ა. (2021). გენდერი და თანამედროვე ქართული თეატრი. ხელოვნება და თანამედროვეობა, ხელოვნებისა და მედიის კვლევების საერთაშორისო კრებული. თეატრისა და კინოს სახელმწიფო უნივერსიტეტის გამომცემლობა „კენტავრი“. #1. (11). (Kvinikadze, A. (2021). Gender and Modern Georgian Theatre. Art and Modernity, International Collection of Art and Media Studies. Publishing House of the State University of Theatre and Cinema "Kentavri". #1. (11).) p. 27.

⁸ Strindberg A. (2007) Preface to *Miss Julie*, Strindberg on Drama and Theatre (selected, translated, and edited by Egil

Törnqvist and Birgitta Steene), „Amsterdam University Press“. p. 65.

⁹ კვინიკაძე, ა. (2021). გენდერი და თანამედროვე ქართული თეატრი. ხელოვნება და თანამედროვეობა, ხელოვნებისა და მედიის კვლევების საერთაშორისო კრებული. თეატრისა და კინოს სახელმწიფო უნივერსიტეტის გამომცემლობა „კენტავრი“. #1. (11). (Kvinikadze, A. (2021). Gender and Modern Georgian Theatre. Art and Modernity, International Collection of Art and Media Studies. Publishing House of the State University of Theatre and Cinema "Kentavri". #1. (11).) p. 27.

self-establishment between people begins, which will end tragically.

Describing Miss Julie, the playwright writes: „The half-woman is a type who thrusts herself forward and sells herself nowadays for power, decorations, honors or diplomas as she used to for money. She represents degeneration. It is not a sound species for it does not last, but unfortunately propagates its misery in the following generation. And degenerate men unconsciously seem to select among them so that they increase in number and produce creatures of uncertain sex for whom life is a torment. Fortunately, they perish, either because they are out of harmony with reality because their repressed instincts erupt uncontrollably, or because their hopes of attaining equality with men are crushed. The type is tragic, offering the spectacle of a desperate struggle against nature, a tragic legacy of romanticism that is now being dissipated by naturalism, the only aim of which is happiness. And happiness means strong and sound species.“¹⁰

Interestingly, Strindberg characterizes Miss Julie as a half-woman, a weak species that does not have a long life, a spreader of evil, etc. This is interesting because, in the end, Strindberg created the image of a strong person. Julie kills herself in the finale, nevertheless, I think this suicide is not a sign of weakness, but strength.

According to Levan Tsuladze's interpretation, Anna Vasadze's Miss Julie is confident in herself, but even this strong person has certain weaknesses. Her tragic fate was determined by many circumstances: the instincts inherited from a low-class, misanthropic mother; and unsuitable upbringing for a girl - her parents raised her like a man and forced her to do everything that men are taught. The character formed from these circumstances does not submit to any obstacles and wants everything to be subject to her will. The festive mood of a summer night, dancing, menstruation, the absence of the father in the house, the mystery of the night and most importantly the fortuity contributed to the sexual intercourse - a big mistake that should not have happened.

Anna Vasadze's Juli is a charming, beautiful, strong character. The actress sometimes creates the image of a powerful, arrogant woman, and sometimes she portrays a weak, vulnerable person as a result of childhood traumas. Ana Vasadze consistently sculpts her character through in-depth processing and presentation of psychological nuances, with acting skills. The director and the actor worked thoroughly to create the image of Miss Julie. Each gesture, plasticity, movement, facial expression, manner of speech, and tone of voice shows the physical or mental state of the character. The scene of the so-called confession with Jean, when Julie

analyzes her entire past life, is interesting and emotional. She drinks a whole bottle of wine, talking about the traumas got from her parents. It gradually becomes clear why and how she became such a person. Miss Julie's main weakness is the search for love. Her mother did not want her to be born. She has been deprived of love since birth and therefore easily believes Jean's feelings for her. The scene of the curse is emotional – how a weak, vulnerable, ruined person turns into a powerful Fury. Miss Julie smears her face with the blood of her beloved bird, decapitated by Jean, and unleashes her anger on Jean. - „Do you think I can't look at any blood? Do you think I'm so weak? Oh! I'd just like to see your blood and your brains on the chopping block. I'd like to see your whole stock swimming in a lake, like the one there. I believe I could drink out of your skull! I could wash my feet in your chest! I could eat your heart roasted.“¹¹ The actress naturally, without any excesses, moves from one state of mind to another: sometimes she is a cheerful, willful creature; sometimes a trusting, kind person; sometimes a strong, arrogant ruler.

According to Strindberg's description „Jean, the servant, lives on, whereas Miss Julie who cannot live without honor does not. The slave has this advantage over the earl in that he lacks this fatal preoccupation with honor.“¹² In Levan Tsuladze's performance, Paata Papuashvili's Jean is a representative of the lower class, arrogant and at the same with slavish psychology, trying to escape from the social situation in which he was born and raised. He is an educated, handsome, attractive man. Jean is one of those people who go to any lengths to achieve their goals. If honor is the most important thing for Miss Julie, for Jean this concept is an empty word. A representative of a low social class dreams of becoming a hotel owner. Even in his dreams, he always rises to the heights. Jean is a man of dual nature, slavish spirit and arrogance exist in him at the same time; Jean hates and fears his surroundings because they are the ones who know him best and know his secrets. To achieve his goals, he will do anything. He skillfully and consistently lures Miss Julie into a trap. In his relationship with a woman, he is sometimes a charming romantic, sometimes a harsh cynic. He always says what is convenient for him at that moment.

The image of the cook Christine in the interpretation of the director and the actress significantly differs from Strindberg's version. According to Strindberg, „Kristin, finally, is a female slave. Standing over the stove all day has made her subservient and dull. She is like an animal, unconscious, of her hypocrisy, overflowing with morality and religion which serve as a cover and a scapegoat for her sins.“¹³

¹⁰ Strindberg A. (2007) Preface to Miss Julie, Strindberg on Drama and Theatre (selected, translated, and edited by Egil Törnqvist and Birgitta Steene), „Amsterdam University Press“, p. 66.

¹¹ Strindberg, A. (2007) Miss Julie and Other Plays, Modern Library, BL. Boni and Liveright, INC. Publishers. New York. P. 39
<https://dn790001.ca.archive.org/0/items/missjulieotherp100striiala/missjulieotherp100striiala.pdf> (30.09.2024).

¹² Strindberg A. (2007) Preface to Miss Julie, Strindberg on Drama and Theatre (selected, translated, and edited by Egil Törnqvist and Birgitta Steene), „Amsterdam University Press“, p. 67.

¹³ Strindberg A. (2007) Preface to Miss Julie, Strindberg on Drama and Theatre (selected, translated, and edited by Egil Törnqvist and Birgitta Steene), „Amsterdam University Press“, p. 68.

Ana Grigolia's cook Christine is characterized by hypocritical morality and religiosity based on her social class. Her main goal is to get married and have children. She guesses the relationship between Jean and Miss Julie, but remains quiet until the critical moment, silently, surreptitiously watching their flirtation - the screen zooms in on Christine's face. Her jealousy is interestingly depicted by the stripes and hissing sounds that appear when the TV signal is damaged. According to the director's interpretation, the fact that the love affair between Miss Julie and Jean did not continue is among other things due to Christine. Because the maid Christine, will not allow them to take away what belongs to her. After all, she is an „owner“ like all other plebeians. She goes to church to hand over her petty thefts to Jesus Christ and to return home with the feeling of innocence - she is sure that the last ones will enter the kingdom and thus she consoles herself.

Tastefully selected music („Somehow“ by Citizen Cope, „Just“ by Radiohead), scenography, video installations, and choreography – all together create a stunning aura and captivate the audience from the beginning to the end of the performance. Ana Vasadze, Paata Papuashvili, and Ana Grigolia - portray their characters with the highest professionalism.

Levan Tsuladze presented the society on the screen as a faceless crowd, which will condemn Julie. This crowd somehow reminds me of bloodthirsty vampires. The director ended the performance with a terrifying scene – Miss Julie kills herself by shooting herself in the vagina with a gun handed over by Jean. The only weakness of this strong but lonely woman was that she believed in Jean's love, followed her momentary passion, and then, later, she couldn't forgive herself.

Conclusion

Levan Tsuladze transferred the text of the play almost unchanged to the stage. When transforming the text of the play into a stage text, the director changed the faces of Julie and Christine through the tasks given to the actors by moving the accents. They are neither weak, nor „nature's mistakes“, nor „monsters“. Julie and Christine, with different methods, different origins, and erudition fight for their rights, and their future. It is true, that Julie kills herself, but this suicide is not equal to defeat, but to victory. Because Julie is the forerunner of those women who, shortly after her suicide, received the right to participate in elections.

For several years, Levan Tsuladze has been exploring the problem of violence in society with his performances, in which violence against women and

the issues of women's rights occupy an important place. *The Kreutzer Sonata, Crime and Punishment, The Marriage of Figaro* - in the Marjanishvili theatre, *Othello* and *Miss Julie* - in the Theatre Factory 42.

It is often said that the interest in the works of the Swedish playwright increases especially in crises, in a transition period, when moral values are reassessed. When doubt arises in people, the situation of an individual becomes extremely intense in a merciless, unforgiving environment, and he tries to find a way to survive.

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